

Realizing Digital Product Passports with Crowdsourcing Principles: The Case of Sustainable Smart Grids

Konstantinos Voulgaridis
Department of Computer Science
International Hellenic University
Kavala Campus, Greece
kwboulg@cs.ihu.gr

Thomas Lagkas
Department of Computer Science
International Hellenic University
Kavala Campus, Greece
tlagkas@cs.ihu.gr

Dimitris Karampatzakis
Department of Computer Science
International Hellenic University
Kavala Campus, Greece
dkara@cs.ihu.gr

Vasileios Argyriou
Department of Networks and Digital Media
Kingston University
Kingston upon Thames, U.K.
vasileios.argyriou@kingston.ac.uk

Panagiotis Sarigiannidis
Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering
University of Western Macedonia
Kozani, Greece
psarigiannidis@uowm.gr

Abstract—Due to constant technological advancements, Smart Grids have the potential to significantly reduce energy consumption, while providing efficient energy management. However, their implementation requires a thorough collection of data related to procedures of energy generation and distribution, as well as the inclusion of Circular Economy (CE) principles to ensure sustainability. Considering the impact of Industry 5.0, Digital Product Passports (DPPs) are a sufficient solution for the recording, presentation, and circularity of the respective data, combined with suitable crowdsourcing strategies for the integration of real-time data provided by consumers. This paper explores the potential implementation of DPPs, infused with crowdsourcing principles, for smart grid integration, through the design of a fundamental CE framework, which is further supported by a systematic literature review and a reference use-case scenario of its operational flow.

Index Terms—Digital Product Passports, Digital Circular Economy, Smart Grid, Crowdsourcing, Prosumers

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital Circular Economy (CE) has been one of the highest research trends over the last few years, due to its capability and potential of data-driven approaches based on re-functionalities, as well as the implementation of digital technologies that further enhance traditional circular procedures, e.g., monitoring recycling progress, material tracking, and optimization of resources. The result of such processes is the formation of circular data, containing valuable information such as the amount and type of recycled materials used, the possibility of reusability post-lifecycle, the environmental impact of the product or service, or other specific indicators depending on the nature of the distributed products. Vital enablers of such functionalities are the development and implementation of Digital Product Passports (DPPs), containing related circular data throughout the lifecycle of a product or service, and supporting the vision of EU's Green Deal Action Plan [1].

Moreover, as there is significant incremental growth in Digital CE applications and gradual DPP solutions, efficient methodologies for data collection are required to support circularity procedures. Taking into consideration the human-centric approach of Industry 5.0 (I5.0), crowdsourcing and crowdsensing characteristics are two technological approaches being adopted as alternative solutions for sustainable data collection through the engagement of consumers or other designated participatory networks, due to their potential of being implemented in different stages of circular value chains [2].

The energy sector is an additional field with the potential to receive valuable benefits in the context of Digital CE and DPPs. Considering the continuous attempts to research and develop sustainable smart grids by integrating different digital technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), Blockchain, and Big Data, the demand for qualitative and accurate data collection is growing [3]. Indicative examples of such data are related to grid stability, maintained energy storage, energy generation insights, and energy demands [4].

Combining the corresponding approaches into unified solutions enables the deployment of state-of-the-art circular systems that expand into the energy sector, and enhances the construction of technological systems while facilitating the interconnection of different actors within the smart grid ecosystems. As a result, data-driven requirements such as real-time data monitoring on energy consumption, monitoring of conventional and renewable sources, and energy distribution tracking, are fulfilled through the integration of DPPs by strengthening overall sustainability and energy efficiency [5].

Our research paper follows a systematic review, with Google Scholar being used for the collection of published material

with an emphasis on the years between 2019 and 2023 and indexes such as IEEEExplore, ScienceDirect, and Elsevier. The key keywords utilized in our search were “Digital Product Passports”, “Digital Product Passports Energy Sector”, “Digital Product Passports Smart Grid”, “Digital Circular Economy Crowdsourcing”, “Smart Grid Renewable Sources”, “Data-driven Smart Grid”, “Prosumer Crowdsourcing”.

Our main contribution is focused on the presentation of a Digital CE framework with incorporated DPP mechanisms and crowdsourcing principles, suitable for the energy sector, and smart grids specifically. First, we investigate the concept of DPPs and their indicative requirements for effective implementation in the context of Digital CE. We proceed by researching key requirements for smart sustainable energy management and the potential correlation of renewable sources within the structure of smart grids. We then investigate the potential content of an energy sector DPP, through data generated by the main components of smart grids, and continue by studying suitable crowdsourcing mechanisms and strategies. We close our paper with a reference use-case scenario to further enhance the functionality of our suggested framework, as well as the respective conclusion.

II. RELATED WORK

A study on the impact of the proper design in the development of DPPs is presented in [6]. The authors investigate the effects of DPP structure in the exploitation of circularity principles within infrastructures, as well as the importance of data generation and establishment of policies, following an actor-centric approach.

The authors of [7] attempt to address issues related to data quality generated by smart grids. The researchers propose an adaptable framework for improved data quality in the operational flow of smart grids, by classifying vital data dimensions that are correlated to data issues such as incomplete data analytics and inaccurate timestamps.

A solution on the application of Digital CE principles in the proper management of waste generated by electronic products is presented in [8]. The authors investigate the combination of IoT and Blockchain technologies for the proper monitoring of electronic products while implementing crowdsourcing principles for the engagement of consumers in the circular value chain, for enhanced data collection efficiency.

Another interesting solution with an implemented crowdsourcing approach is studied in [9]. The researchers propose a framework capable of optimizing collaborative production and energy consumption in smart grids, through the utilization of Blockchain, while enabling consistent Peer-to-Peer (P2P) energy trading.

III. DIGITAL PRODUCT PASSPORTS

A. Main Concept

DPPs are considered an innovative enabler towards the digitalization of CE, supporting the generation and collection of data related to products and services, such as materials, components, analytics on production and supply chains, as well

as lifecycle predictions during consumption stages. Integration of digital technologies assists in the overall interpretation of the presented data, for enhanced decision-making procedures related to circularity principles and the implementation of re-functionalities [10].

Additionally, due to the ongoing promotion of Digital CE, and its gradual adoption by different sectors, there is a rise in the development and release of regulations, requiring the collection and logging of re-data, to ensure the applicability of circularity within operation flows. As a result, DPPs establish and sustain communication channels between participants of the circular chain, for the creation of detailed datasheets that can be used for impactful optimization such as minimizing the consumption of raw materials, boosting the general economy, and decarbonizing industrial infrastructures [11].

B. Indicative Requirements for implementation

For DPPs to be successfully implemented and effectively support a CE framework, a number of essential conditions need to be satisfied. At its core, the corresponding datasheet serves as a tool for the collection, storage, and dissemination of data related to the overall environmental, social, and economic impact of a product or service. Consequently, it must be distinguished by interoperability, security, and accessibility toward the participating stakeholders in order to accomplish its purpose. In Table I we provide key implementation requirements, by taking into consideration the ones studied in [12] and [13].

TABLE I: Key requirements for the implementation of DPPs

DPP Requirements	Description
Detailed Information	Providing thorough and standardized data and information on production and supply chain procedures, product or service composition, usecycle, lifecycle, circularity, and environmental impact.
Collaboration among stakeholders	Providing data availability, transparency, and sharing between producers, partners, and other relevant stakeholders of the circular value chain, while initiating common agreements on the traceability of confidential data.
Data Identification	Exploitation of proper digital technologies for the interconnection of data with physical products through specialized identification codes and certifications for additional control, as well as data visualization methodologies.
Regulatory Compliance	Obliging to regulations related to the structure and content of DPPs, such as EU’s Green Deal and Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), as well as in the special cases where a DPP must be issued.

C. Enabling technologies

Further supporting the importance of data within Digital CE systems, implementing suitable technologies for their collection, curation, sharing, and leveraging facilitates the establishment of I5.0 environments with integrated DPP functionalities. Table II presents a collection of technologies enabling the formation of DPPs, considering the material published in [14], [15], [16], and [17].

TABLE II: Key Enabling Technologies for the formation of DPPs

Digital Technologies	Functionality
IoT	Essential technology for monitoring performance, and collection of data by utilizing sensory devices, QR codes, or RFID tags, through the different stages of a circular value chain
AI – ML	Utilized for the identification and categorization of the required and desired data or information, as well as their automated collection
Digital Twins	Assisting in an efficient data collection manner, by utilizing the digitalized versions of the targeted physical counterparts for the required monitoring procedures
Digital Threads	Providing efficient interconnection of procedures, layers, and databases throughout the lifecycle of products and services
Blockchain	Ensures the integrity, traceability, and security of the utilized data, both before and after the collection phase, while interconnecting the different components and actors of the circular value chain
IOTA	Supports the monitoring of the origin, ownership, and usecycle of data, products, and services, while offering an immutable ledger, enhanced decentralization, and secure zero-fee transactions between stakeholders.

IV. DIGITAL CE IN SMART GRIDS

A. Indicative Requirements for Smart Energy Management

The development and implementation of smart grids are essential for the transition and establishment of more sustainable and efficient energy systems. Such infrastructures are accomplished with the integration and combination of digital technologies to effectively support procedures such as energy production and distribution while taking into consideration all of the interconnected components, actors, and their respective requirements. To further understand the conditions of such systems, we provide a thorough list with an analysis of their corresponding requirements, as stated in [18], [19], [20], and [21]:

- **Renewable Sources of Energy:** Smart Grids have the capability of integrating renewable sources of energy within their architecture, as part of specifically designed microgrids, that are interconnected within the complete distribution system. As a result, remote green energy storage is enabled, while minimizing greenhouse emissions, consumption of raw materials, and energy production costs.
- **Digital Technologies:** Technologies such as IoT, Big Data, AI, and Blockchain are vital for the interconnection of automated components, monitoring of massive real-time data, secure transactions, and supporting prosumer features. Similarly, smart metering devices are essential for secure energy monitoring and data collection, both for the producers and consumers.
- **Self-Healing:** Considered a by-product of digital technologies, self-healing ensures automated detection of energy-related and cyber-security issues, while isolating the corresponding failures for proper handling, resulting in

minimization of impact on consumers, financial losses, and data breaches.

- **Consumer Engagement:** Smart grids enable features such as Demand Side Management (DSM), Demand Response (DR), and prosumers. Data related to the prices and energy consumption is provided to consumers, allowing them to consider their energy demands. As a result, capabilities regarding scheduled distribution, consumption efficiency, and lower costs are enabled. Additionally, prosumers can provide impactful energy balancing through excessive or renewable energy sharing with other users by connecting to the corresponding microgrids.
- **Security-Privacy:** Due to the ongoing communication between the stakeholders of a smart grid, ensuring the privacy and confidentiality of data, as well as established security mechanisms in the network’s architectural layers are highly required. Agreements on personal data rights and implementation of regulations such as “Data Protection Directive 95/46/EC” by the European Commission must be implemented.
- **Reliability:** Alternative solutions and countermeasures need to be installed in the system’s infrastructure to ensure ongoing functionality of the smart grid in the case of possible failures, by employing suitable IoT mechanisms to monitor the reliability of the corresponding system. Significant examples are the availability of alternative data streams, countermeasures for energy outages, monitoring hybrid energy generation in microgrids, etc.

B. Smart Grid-related data on DPPs

Smart grid-generated data are essential for providing thorough insights into procedures related to energy generation, distribution, and consumption, by assisting in decision-making actions related to optimization, efficient integration of renewable energy sources, and increased reliability. Moreover, considering a consumer-centric perspective, such data can assist in identifying energy-saving opportunities, billing overviews, and evaluation of prosumer procedures. The following list presents key types of data generated by smart grids, as stated in [22], [23], and [24], that have the potential of supporting the formation of DPPs related to smart energy management.

1) Energy Generation:

- Consumption of materials for energy generation, e.g. coal in tones (ton), oil in liters (lt), or natural gas in cubic meters (m^3)
- Amount of generated energy in kilowatts per hour (kWh) or megawatts per hour (MWh)
- Efficiency and functionality of the utilized equipment for energy generation in percentage (%)
- Amount of Greenhouse Emissions generated in tonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent (tCO_2e)

2) Renewable Energy Integration:

- Type of renewable source, e.g., solar, wind, or hydroelectric
- Amount of renewable energy generated in kilowatts per hour (kWh) or megawatts per hour (MWh)

- Environmental conditions depending on the type of renewable energy source used, e.g., temperature in Celcius (°C), wind speed in meters per second (m/s), flow rate of water in cubic meters per second (m³/s)
- Amount of equipment used for each source, e.g., photovoltaic panels, wind turbines, and hydroelectric power plants, and their geolocation
- Efficiency and functionality of the utilized equipment for renewable energy generation in percentage (%)
- Microgrid integration status with detailed data on the grid stability

3) *Energy Transmission:*

- Type and amount of equipment used for transmission and distribution e.g., transformers, substations, transmission, and distribution lines, as well as their geolocation
- Amount of energy being distributed through the transmission equipment in kilowatts (kW), megawatts (MW), or gigawatts (GW)
- Efficiency and functionality of the utilized equipment for energy distribution in percentage (%)
- Amount of energy lost during energy distribution in kilowatts (kW), megawatts (MW), or gigawatts (GW)

4) *Grid Management:*

- Status and functionality of the overall grid and its components in percentage (%), including outage and fault detection
- Amount of conventional and renewable energy being used within the grid in percentage (%)
- Forecasting of energy demands within the grid
- Real-time updating of energy prices in euros per kilowatt per hour or megawatt per hour (€/kWh or €/MWh)

5) *Smart Metering:*

- Amount of energy consumed in kilowatts per hour (kWh) or megawatts per hour (MWh)
- Quality of distributed energy depending on fluctuations
- Peak amount of energy demand and consumption, as well as timestamps of the corresponding moments
- Amounts of renewable and conventional energy consumed.

6) *Prosumer Processes:*

- Amount of energy stored for utilization in kilowatts per hour (kWh) or megawatts per hour (MWh)
- Amount of energy exported to other consumers in kilowatts per hour (kWh) or megawatts per hour (MWh)
- Amount of energy exported back to the grid in kilowatts per hour (kWh) or megawatts per hour (MWh)
- Amount of consumers adopting prosumer roles, as well as the number of consumers purchasing energy from prosumers
- Energy pricing from prosumer procedures in euro (€)

V. CROWDSOURCING APPROACHES ON SMART GRIDS

A. *Main Concept of energy crowdsourcing*

Due to the constant evolution of smart grids, the ongoing implementation of circularity principles for the establishment

of sustainable practices in the energy sector, as well as the need for increased involvement of IS.0 characteristics, energy crowdsourcing has been a major innovative action promoting a healthy collaboration between energy producers, utility companies, and consumers. One of the most common approaches in the corresponding case is the adoption of the role of prosumer, through the formation of microgrids and the option of commercializing surplus energy or related data to other consumers or energy producers, while maintaining a circular motion [25].

Numerous types of business models are currently available combining the concept of prosumers with traditional crowdsourcing principles. An indicative example is presented in [26], through the net metering model, where the prosumer is responsible for his personal energy generation while storing excess energy for injection into the main smart grid of a utility company. As a result, the prosumer receives monetized credits that can be used for the reduction of his monthly energy billings.

Another example following the same concepts is researched in [27], where the researchers investigate the case of the Omni-Sharing business model, in which the system involves the utilization of ride-sharing electric vehicles to crowdsource energy from a community of prosumers. The corresponding model follows two sharing approaches, external between prosumers and the electric vehicles, and internal among the prosumers while taking into consideration the profitability of both parties. To further motivate the participation of prosumers within the formed grid, the model utilizes the cooperative game theory ensuring cost minimization and ongoing collaborations.

A traditional approach to the role of prosumers is presented in [28]. The researchers propose a bidding-based model, which is consisted of participating prosumers, undergoing a bidding process for acquiring energy assets in certain timeslots. Additionally, a game-based analysis is conducted to investigate the trustfulness of the system, considering the potential strategic intentions of the participating prosumers, as well as the formation of incentives for reduced energy billings.

B. *Indicative crowdsourcing strategies*

An important consideration in the adoption of crowdsourcing principles within an architecture or framework is a thorough investigation of strategies and mechanisms that will assist in the continuous attraction of crowdsourcing participants. Incentive mechanisms are an essential component of the corresponding case since they are key indicators for motivating users to participate, as well as maintaining their involvement in the predetermined task, as seen in the prosumer examples mentioned above. According to [29], there are two main categories of incentive mechanisms, intrinsic which correlate to emotional and ethical rewards, and extrinsic such as monetary rewards.

Following up on this particular statement, we research the different approaches to extrinsic and intrinsic incentive mechanisms, according to their resulting rewards toward the participating users of the crowdsourced system. Table III presents these types of strategies, classified into their corresponding incentive type, as also studied in [30], [31], [32], and [33]

TABLE III: Indicative Crowdsourcing Incentive Mechanisms

Incentives Approach	Type	Description
Monetary Rewards	Extrinsic	It is considered one of the most traditional and effective approaches related to crowdsourcing systems. In the context of data collection for the case of DPPs, the rewarding mechanism is dependent on the amount of data that the user is willing to share, usually in the form of an auctioning system. Indicative examples of monetary rewards are credit earnings, billing discounts, or a small monetary price per data submitted.
Service-Based Mechanism	Extrinsic	It is defined by its collaborative nature and the sense of mutual advantage. Similar to the fundamental concept of prosumers, in this particular case, the crowdsourcing participants are able to request or submit services with other participating actors, promoting the collaboration between users for the fulfillment of certain tasks of interest.
Gamified Techniques	Intrinsic	Aiming towards correlating the predefined task fulfillment with the user's entertainment, the corresponding methods adopt gamification mechanisms, such as rankings and leaderboards, point earnings, and experience bars. Comparing it to monetary incentives, gamified rewards are dependent on the user's performance in order to motivate them for increased engagement.
Sense of honor	Intrinsic	Being one of the most impactful incentives, the particular strategy promotes social responsibility. Different cases of promoting ethical consciousness are the promotion of social or environmental impact, with the user's engagement assisting in a positive change of the original cause or charitable-based outcomes where participation will lead to monetary donations or other philanthropic actions.

VI. REFERENCE IMPLEMENTATION OF DPPs AND CROWDSOURCING IN AN ENERGY GENERATION COMPANY

Supported by the requirements investigated in the previous sections, in Fig. 1 we present a potential framework for Smart Grid implementation in the context of an energy generation company, with an emphasis on DPP integration and crowdsourcing principles, while supporting Digital CE characteristics. Specifically, it supports the generation of two passport versions: Business Passport and User Passport, while combining both intrinsic and extrinsic incentive mechanisms. The specific framework is separated into three different layers:

a) Data collection, b) DPP formation, and c) end-client and prosumer stage, with the presented figure depicting the utilized technologies in cloud shapes, and the blue lines representing the establishment of Digital Threads. The following subsections describe the functionality of each component, including the selected digital technologies for their fulfillment.

A. Data Collection Phase

We assume that the corresponding energy generation company utilizes both conventional means of energy generation in the form of power plants while supplementing additional energy requirements through renewable sources. As investigated in the previous sections, such processes generate a number of data e.g., resources and materials available for energy generation, equipment status, amounts of energy consumption for the corresponding generation, costs, profits, and additional requirements from renewable sources. As a result, the company proceeds with two simultaneous processes, the generation of electricity through conventional methods, and the generation of energy through renewable sources for supplementation.

Starting with the generation of energy through power plants, the utilization of Digital Twins assists in the simulation of the overall performance of the indicative power plants, as well as the interconnected substations and transmission lines. Such technologies support the efficient optimization and management of the upcoming generation process in terms of energy requirements, resources for the generation process, and efficient distribution of energy, through the implementation of ML algorithms for accurate prediction of resource needs. The generated dataset can be used for future comparisons to potential optimization process updates.

Simultaneously, hypothesizing that the company follows environmental-friendly policies, it supplements distributed energy requirements through the utilization of renewable energy sources, either by power plants owned by the company or other partners. More importantly, IoT sensory devices are installed in the renewable energy generators, to monitor performance and generation rate, amount of generated energy, the status of the equipment, and environmental conditions related to the indicative source.

The partners of the respective company range from resource and equipment suppliers for the proper functionality and energy generation of the initial power plant, to independent companies owning exclusively renewable energy plants that focus on supplementing the producer's energy requirements. Data related to available resources, cost of materials, available renewable energy for distribution, and respective prices, are exchanged through the utilization of Blockchain and IOTA for secure and decentralized trading while clarifying ownership of the shared energy percentage.

Overall, processes related to energy production, partners, substations, and transmission lines are interconnected through the implementation of Digital Threads, with the related data being collected and stored in the company's private cloud. To ensure optimal organization and to remove any extraneous noise, the stored data go through extensive preprocessing. This

Fig. 1: Diagram of a potential Smart Grid framework

helps to prevent mistakes about expenses, profitability, resource requirements, and the amount of distributed energy that is accessible.

B. DPPs formation

Proceeding to the passport generation phase, the pre-processed data are used to form the full version of the Business Passport, accessed by the energy generation company and the respective partners. The Business Passport consists of a thoroughly organized dataset of costs and profits of material and resource requirements, the status of equipment both in terms of the producing entity and partners, available generated energy, available renewable energy, investor-related statistics, etc. Moreover, data related to the distributed network of substations and transmission lines are also included e.g., the status of substations and transmission and power lines, areas

covered, amounts of distributed energy, and clarification on percentages regarding generated and renewable energies.

Then, an automated AI sorting process extracts the required data to form the respective User Passport, which is exclusively created for consumers and prosumers, consisting of the status of the locally linked transmission lines and substations, the amount of distributed renewable energy to the consumer, the consumption and cost of spent energy, as well as the amount of excess energy.

C. End-clients and prosumers stage

Finally, the distribution of energy is achieved through the substations and transmission lines assigned to each covering space. Additionally, the installation of smart metering devices in consumers' properties further supports the updates of User Passports, while enabling and further enhancing the role of prosumers. The consumers access the User Passport through

the owned smart metering and depending on the amount of excessive and unneeded energy, they have the option of sharing it with other consumers for commercial use or returning it to the producer. The corresponding stage enables a two-way system, by implementing incentive mechanisms, such as monetary rewards and service-based strategies, as well as ethical responsibility towards the environmental impact of CE, to promote participation in the grid's circularity.

Starting with the consumer's decision to return the energy surplus back to the main grid, smart contracts are established between the producer and client, to further support the corresponding infusion and enable access to the user's private data through the User Passport e.g., daily consumption practices and habits, timestamps, individual consumption of devices. As a reward, a credit system is enabled with each credit corresponding to the amount of data and energy of the consumer's contribution submitted, which can later be used for billing discounts.

Regarding the decision of the consumer to adopt the role of prosumer, a micro-grid supported by IOTA functionalities is established within the main grid. Due to the corresponding microgrid being part of the producer's main grid, the provided functionalities are accompanied by restricted rights, while maintaining the mutual interests and advantages of both the producer and prosumers. The prosumer submits his energy availability and costs within the decentralized network, with consumers submitting their interest and request to purchase that energy. Upon agreement, the decentralized microgrid is formed between the prosumer and the consumer.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we discuss the potential implementation of DPPs and crowdsourcing characteristics on smart grids, through the presentation of a reference framework applied in the context of an energy generation company. We researched the indicative technological and implementation requirements for the formation of DPPs, the essential requirements for effective smart energy management, the different types of smart grid data generated for DPP integration, as well as important and practical crowdsourcing strategies. As part of our future work, we intend to investigate the practicality of IOTA as an effective Digital Thread and decentralized solution, the suitable integration of AI for efficient extraction and sorting of data, and the potentiality of implementing smaller-scaled IOTA networks within the main IOTA infrastructure.

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